

ASSESSING DELAMINATION GROWTH UNDER CYCLIC LOADING

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ABSTRACT

To progress towards a slow-growth design basis for aircraft composite structures, the growth of typical damages must be predictable under service conditions. A review of limited experimental data available in the literature, mainly uniaxial coupon data, shows that the growth of delaminations or disbonds under cyclic loading is systematic and thus should be predictable. One such prediction was made here using a variant of the Hartman-Schijve equation. In the cases considered here, a simple metric namely delamination/debond length correlated to the number of cycles applied. Further investigations are required, particularly of representative aircraft structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite airframes are currently predominantly designed using the “no growth” design philosophy. This design methodology is built around a “building block” approach. Consequently questions arise: What happens if, although there was no damage growth during the “building block” tests or in the full scale fatigue tests, disbonds and or delaminations are found in operational aircraft? Furthermore, what happens when an airframe, which was designed under a no growth design philosophy, has exceeded its design life?

These questions, and others, have subsequently led to a growing interest in moving towards a slow-growth design approach that could form the basis for the in-service sustainment management of composite or bonded aircraft structures. For such a (slow growth) approach to be feasible there is a need to establish whether the growth of typical damage (e.g. delaminations) in such structure is systematic, and therefore potentially predicable. To this end this paper summarizes some data from the literature, and draws some general conclusion from this review. It is concluded (from the limited data available) that the growth of delaminations under cyclic loading is systematic and thus should be predictable. Further it considers the utility of the Hartman-Schijve delamination growth equation to predict the growth of delaminations.

A conclusion reached in this paper is the scarcity of data associated with delamination and disbond growth in representative aircraft structures subjected to realistic multi-axial stress states.

2 BACKGROUND

Some of the potential benefits of slow-growth concepts for composite structures include potentially lighter designs and improved aircraft availability through allowing damage to remain in-service for a prescribed time. Before these can be achieved, the growth of typical damage (production or in-service) must be shown to be predictable. A tool-set capturing the growth behavior is then required (as well as non-destructive inspection techniques etc.).

A review of limited publically available data for the growth of delaminations in composites or adhesively bonded joints was performed ([1]); however, accurate and well documented data appears relatively rare, particularly when one considers the wide range of material types, applications, loading conditions, and failure mechanisms that should be considered in designing composite structures. It is noted that this data was mainly restricted to uniaxial-loaded flat coupons containing simulated delaminations. Some of the damage/delamination growth data versus number of cycles observations are presented below (the data was digitized from the literature and thus subject to human error). It appears that the limited data suggests that damage growth is predictable, and a variant of the Hartman-Schijve equation is shown to capture the growth trend in one case.

3 DELAMINATION GROWTH DATA

Some simulated delamination/debond growth metric (e.g. delamination length) versus cycles data is presented below (this is additional to that presented in [1][2]).

Case 1:

The objective of this investigation was to shed some light onto skin/stringer fatigue debond failure [7]. Four-point bending fatigue tests at a cyclic frequency of 5 Hz and a stress ratio R of 0.1 on simulated skin/stringer flat-coupons were conducted for load levels corresponding to 40%, 50%, 60%, 70% and 80% of the monotonic fracture load, P_{nl} . The configuration of the specimens is summarised in Table 1. Both the skin and flange were made from IM6/3501-6 graphite/epoxy prepreg tape with a nominal ply thickness of 0.188 mm. The flange was adhesively bonded to the skin using a 177 °C cure film adhesive from America Cyanamid (CYTEC 1515). A Grade 5 film of the adhesive was used to yield a nominally 0.127 mm thick bondline. No attempt to account for secondary bending was made. From the monotonic tests P_{nl} was determined at which the load versus stroke curves deviated slightly from the initial linear slope.

Table 1 - Laminate characteristics.

Lay-up	Skin (S)/Flange (F)	Thickness, mm	Bending Stiffness D_{11} , Nm
S1	[45/-45/0/0/45/90/-45] _s	2.8	112
S3	[90/45/0/0/-45/45/-45/90] _s	3.0	117
F1	[45/90/-45/0/90] _s	2.0	22.5

Configuration A = S1 + F1

Configuration D = S3 + F1

Delaminations (labelled "B" for bondline failures) were noted to form from matrix cracks. These "B" delaminations ran to one side of the interface between the bondline and the composite, usually the top skin ply interface. The first delamination always corresponded to the first matrix crack that formed. They were followed by delaminations between plies (labelled "P") at corners 1 and 4 (Figure 1). Some data is shown Figure 2 to Figure 3.

Figure 1: Four point bending specimen with delamination location and surface ply orientations marked (from [7])

Figure 2: Log delamination length versus number of cycles for specimen-type A at $P_{max} = 80\% P_{nl}$ (adapted from Fig 10 & Fig 11 in [7])

Case 2:

Bisagni et al. considered two specimens with two bonded laminates and tested in 4-point bending fatigue [8]. The first rectangular laminate was 2 mm thick, 100 mm wide and 200 mm long. In the central part a second laminate was co-bonded using an adhesive. The second laminate was 2 mm thick, and both the width and length were equal to 100 mm.

Figure 3: Log delamination length versus number of cycles for specimen-type A at $P_{max} = 50\%$ and $60\% P_{nl}$ (adapted from Fig14 to Fig 17 in [7])

The laminates were manufactured from M21/T800S UD carbon/epoxy prepreg tape from Hexcel, with a nominal ply thickness of 0.193 mm and a fibre mass of 198 g/m² as well as 0.12mm and fibre mass of 134g/m². The laminates consisted of 10 plies with a stacking sequence: $[45/-45/0/90/0]_s$, when the thicker plies were used and 16 plies with a stacking sequence: $[45/-45/0/90/-45/45/0/90]_s$, when the lower thickness plies were used, both resulting in a thickness of 2 mm. For the bonding of the laminates a high shear strength modified epoxy adhesive from Cytec was used.

In order to study the influence of an embedded defect at the bonding layer, the specimens contained a 7 mm Teflon insert at the adhesive level in one side of the specimens. In the specimens with (Redundant High-Efficiency Assembly) RHEA, the reinforcements were spaced about 14 mm along the edges of the flange, where the highest shear stresses occur and the damage is more likely to develop. The growth data taken visually from the specimens' sides are shown in Figure 4.

Case 3:

The material system chosen for this study was woven-roving E-glass fibre supplied by Fibre Glass Industries (FGI) with FGI's super 317 [6]. The fabric designation was FGI 1854 with 18 oz/square yard areal weight and an unbalanced construction. The vinyl ester resin used was brominated Dow Chemicals Derakane 510A-40. The resin had a 350 cps viscosity at room temperature, which was considered ideally suited for vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding (VARTM).

A 10ply 0-deg laminate with a 0.5 mil Kaptan insert at the mid-plane to simulate a delamination was fabricated by a VARTM process. The panel was approximately 810 mm wide, 328 mm length with a delamination length of 64 mm.

The double cantilever beam fatigue delamination growth test was used. The test was conducted under constant amplitude block cyclic displacement loading at the frequency range of 1-4 Hz with an R of 0.1. The data is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4: Debond crack length versus cycles for T-series (co-bonded with Teflon insert) and FBRK-series (co-bonded with RHEA and Teflon insert) tested under 4-point bending. Minimum load = 200 N, Maximum load = 2000N (adapted from Fig 14 in [8]).

Figure 5: Delamination growth data adapted from Figs 9 and 11 in Chen et al. [6]

Block loading 1 was considered a typical in-service loading experienced by a structural component. It consisted of increasing $G_{I_{max}}$ from 0.3 to $0.5G_{IC}$, holding $G_{I_{max}}$ constant at $0.5G_{IC}$, and decreasing $G_{I_{max}}$ from 0.5 to $0.3G_{IC}$. Each of these segments was applied over 100k cycles with a total of 300k load cycles.

Block loading 2 was a more aggressive, as the loading G_{Imax} was increased from $0.2G_{\text{IC}}$ to $1.4G_{\text{IC}}$ (sic: as stated in [6]) in the first 30k cycles, held constant at $1.4G_{\text{IC}}$ for another 25k cycles and decreased from $1.4G_{\text{IC}}$ to $0.4G_{\text{IC}}$ in the final 25k cycles.

Case 4:

An experimental study was conducted to examine the debond growth in carbon fibre reinforced aluminium laminates (CARALL) under uniaxial cyclic loading [9]. The growth rate of debonding between the aluminium sheets and the fibre/epoxy composite core was measured as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Development of delamination cracks in the interface between bonded metallic sheets and a composite laminate under cyclic loading ($\Delta\sigma = 198$ MPa, $R = 0.1$) is shown as a function of fatigue cycles, where the lengths of four delamination cracks in a specimen are shown (adapted from Fig 4 in [9]) (note: locations of a-d not defined)

3.1 Discussion

The above figures (coupled with other results reported in [1][2]) show for tests under bending fatigue that there appears to be a general trend of early rapid growth, and in many instances, followed by plateauing of the growth rate. It would also appear that the plateau points shifts to the right with decreasing P_{nl} . (The cause of the plateau may be a different phenomenon for debonds and delamination and this requires further investigation). From this we conclude that the growth is systematic (albeit with some degree of scatter between nominally identical geometries and loading). Note that the maximum cycles shown did not equate to specimen failure.

4 COMPUTING DAMAGE GROWTH

Up until recently most fracture mechanics based approaches to computing the growth of delamination damage under fatigue loads were based on assuming that the growth rate da/dN is a function of ΔG [2]. However, as explained in [4], [5] this approach is inherently flawed and is not consistent with the Paris crack growth equation as developed for metals.

This has led to the development of the Hartman-Schijve variant of the NASGRO crack growth equation [4], viz:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = D \left[\frac{\Delta\sqrt{G} - \Delta\sqrt{G_{thr}}}{\sqrt{\{1 - \sqrt{G_{max}}/\sqrt{A}\}}} \right]^n \quad (1)$$

where D and n are constants and the terms A and $\Delta\sqrt{G}$ are best interpreted as a parameters chosen so as to fit the experimentally-measured data. An illustration of this can be seen for the DCB test reported in [6] involving a E-glass vinyl-ester resin laminate (data shown earlier in Figure 5).

Figure 7: Comparison between measured and predicted delamination growth histories, from [11].

However, [11] has shown that when, as in [5], da/dN is reformulated as a function of G_{max} , then crack growth in this material can be expressed as per Eqn (2) with $D = 1.13 \times 10^{-6}$, $p = 1.8$ and $G_{max,thr} = 180 \text{ J/m}^2$.

$$da/dN = D[(\sqrt{G_{max}} - \sqrt{G_{max,thr}})/\sqrt{(1 - \sqrt{G_{max}}/G_c)}]^p \quad (2)$$

As noted in [6] G_c has a strong R curve dependency: increasing from an initial value of approximately 320 J/m^2 to approximately 900 J/m^2 as the delamination length increases. Therefore, [11] used the $G_c(R)$ curve given in [6] when computing da/dN . The resultant measured and computed delamination curves are shown in Figure 7. Here it can be seen the crack growth history computed using the Hartman-Schijve equation yields a crack length history that is in excellent agreement with the measured experimental data.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Whilst limited experimental data is available in the literature, this uniaxial coupon data shows that the growth of delaminations or disbonds under cyclic loading is systematic and thus should be predictable. One such prediction was made here using a variant of the Hartman-Schijve equation. In the cases considered here, a simple metric namely delamination/debond length correlated to the number of cycles applied. Further investigations are required particularly for the growth of damage in representative aircraft structures under representative multi-axial stresses, structures and to determine whether practical inspection intervals can be achieved.

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REFERENCES

- [1] L. Molent and C. Forrester, The lead crack concept applied to defect growth in aircraft composite structures, *Composite Structures*, **166**, 2017, pp. 22-26.
- [2] R. Jones, A.J. Kinloch, J.G. Michopoulos., A.J. Brunner and N. Phan, Delamination growth in polymer-matrix fibre composites and the use of fracture mechanics data for material characterisation and life prediction, *Composite Structures*, **180**, 2017, pp. 316-333.
- [3] CMH-17-3G, Composite Materials Handbook, Volume 3: Polymer Matrix Composites Materials Usage, Design and Analysis, Published by SAE International, March 2012.
- [4] R. Jones, A.J. Kinloch, W. Hu, Cyclic-fatigue crack growth in composite and adhesively-bonded structures: the FAA slow crack growth approach to certification and the problem of similitude, *International Journal of Fatigue*, **88**, 2016, pp. 10-18.
- [5] C. Rans, R. Alderliesten and R. Benedictus Misinterpreting the results: how similitude can improve our understanding of fatigue delamination growth, *Compos Sci Technol*, **71**, 2011, pp. 230–238.
- [6] H. Chen, K. Shivakumar and F. Abali, A comparison of total fatigue life models for composite laminates, *Fatigue Fract Engng Mater Struct*, **29**, pp. 31–39, 2006.
- [7] M.K. Cvitkovich, T.K. O'Brien and P.J. Minguet, (1997) Fatigue debonding characterization in composite skin/stringer configurations, *NASA Technical Memorandum* 110331, Virginia, USA
- [8] C. Bisagni, D. Furfari and M. Pacchione, *Fatigue and Damage Tolerance Assessment of 3-D reinforced CFRP Bonded Joints*, 28th ICAF Symposium, Helsinki, 3–5 June 2015
- [9] C.T. Lin and P.W. Kao, Fatigue delamination growth in carbon fibre-reinforced aluminium laminates, *Composites*, 1996; A 21A, pp. 9- 15.
- [10] R. Jones and D. Hui, *Analysis, design and assessment of composite repairs to operational aircraft*, Chapter 8, pp. 325-456, Aircraft Sustainment and Repair, Edited by R. Jones, N. Matthews, A.A. Baker and V. Champagne Jr., Butterworth-Heinemann Press, 2018, ISBN 9780081005408.
- [11] R. Jones, J.G. Michopoulos, A.J. Kinloch, A.P. Iliopoulos, D. Peng 1, N. Phan and J. Lua, Damage Assessment in Composite and Bonded Airframe, *Proceedings AIAC 2018: 18th Australian International Aerospace Congress*, Melbourne 24 - 28th February, Published by Engineers Australia, Royal Aeronautical Society, 2019, pp. 301-306.